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Expert views on interdisciplinarity in engineering education for design of a new modern University.

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ABSTRACT

University education, and particularly engineering education, is currently undergoing intensive change. A number of new universities have been established in recent years to fulfil modern educational model in STEM. Current research effort reports the finding of a recent study commissioned by a private foundation with a goal to establish a new engineering university in Europe. The experts converged on several important components for a new university to be successful: (a) highly personalized educational plan, with an ability to combine completely different modules from STEM, art, history, real-life projects etc.; (b) return to the origin of liberal arts envisioning a university as a bearer of the European humanistic tradition; (c) multidisciplinary education program in complex socio-technical systems with strong emphasis on data science; (d) distributed and cross-border campus and individual adaptive educational scenarios. The findings of this study highlight global trends in higher education affecting most university models and STEM education as a whole.

1. INTRODUCTION

University education, and engineering education in particular, is currently going through the period of intensive change. A number of new universities have been established in recent years to fulfil modern educational model in STEM [1, 2, 3]. Often such new universities are privately funded initiatives. Current research effort reports the finding of a recent study commissioned by a private foundation with a goal to establish a new engineering university in Europe. The purpose of the study was to identify significant global trends in education and to develop recommendations for setting up a model for a next generation university capable of

creating an environment sufficiently fertile for the development of an intellectual elite suitable to the modern world. Preference was given to the recommendations relevant to the Minimal Viable Product (MVP) concept.

2. METHODS

The data for the study was collected between November 2017 and March 2018. Three qualitative research methods were utilized in the study: twenty semi structured in-depth interviews were conducted with international experts from academia, business, art and policymakers from EU, USA and Russia.

In this paper we report on the fraction of the study related to the experts' perspective on local and global trends in higher education.

Expert interviews provided an opportunity to get acquainted with the respondents' opinions on three topics: first, to discuss economic and social processes that influence the education system and how the education system in general and higher educational institutions in particular respond to these processes; second, to understand what innovations are developing in modern universities and what new projects and models of activity within these the universities have been successful and why; third, to find out what the respondents think about launching a new, next generation university, what features they consider necessary for success and what key risks they see in this project

During the study, 20 expert interviews were conducted, and a list of experts is provided in Appendix 1.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Current chapter will report the research finding in terms of the expert views on current situation in Higher education, mission of a contemporary university and a vision of a successful university of the nearest 10-15 years.

3.1. Current Situation in Higher Education

The experts believe, that current higher education situation is characterized by intensive competition between universities and between universities and business, massification of higher education with the risk of quality decrease, and a boom of online education as one of the solutions to address the problem of quality maintenance while meeting the increased need of higher education graduates. Other trends, i.e. internationalization, implementation of quality assurance procedures, and life-long learning described as existing trends in e.g. *Trends 2010: A decade of change in European Higher Education* [4], by the respondent of this research were reported as desirable, and as the features of a “future” university, rather than currently observed trends.

3.1.1. Competition escalation

The experts noticed that, globalization of economy, massification of higher education and growing mobility of students and professors all over the world have led to fiercer competition for talent and resources, increases in the level of necessary investment.

The increase in university education costs due to the growth of its scale and increased price of material factors of conducting scientific research puts a lot of pressure on national budgets [5].

«I think that there is a stratification dilemma here, as in the whole world. What will happen — on the one hand, large universities will still exist — elite universities that will respond to certain needs, either intellectual or practical. But here the role of the middle ones, as if becoming the case all over the world (in other spheres), disappears; the middle class — it goes away everywhere. The same thing happens with universities. (...) Polarization and stratification, this is a slightly different topic... Big and small will remain, and the middle-sized ones will go away».

Besides, the respondents of this research report that contemporary universities are forced to compete with large corporations for researchers:

“Many corporations — Facebook, Amazon, Google and other companies of the new economy — are recruiting large groups of researchers who will be involved in exactly the same kind of work they would be doing at universities. Working for these corporations is prestigious, and this work is well paid”.

In the experts' view, currently applied tenure system is out of date:

«Some approaches — like the tenure system, for example, in the United States — have been effective before, but have already fulfilled their role and in the current situation hold everyone back»

3.1.2. Massification of higher education and risks for quality

Another characteristic of higher education situation pointed out by the experts, is increased need for higher education degrees for successful performance in jobs. The increasing complexity of production technologies, the rapid development of information technology, the pace of growth in the development and implementation of new products and services in production and daily life all combine to demand recognition of a pressing need for higher education on a global scale than ever existed before [6]. The rapid growth in the number of universities and students has led to a significant variety in the quality of education and the types of university models than those which sufficed in the past.

«In India about 3000 new engineering schools were created in the last 5 years. Proceeding from the fact that the effectiveness of teaching depends directly on the quality of the teaching staff, one can only guess at what this current level of effectiveness is. But nevertheless it speaks about the scale of demand».

3.1.3. Online Boom

Finally, the respondents notice that online technology has increasingly become part of the routine process at universities. Now students can master standard courses online, and time in a classroom can be used more efficiently for discussion and verification of the knowledge obtained.

On the other hand, according to the experts, the development of online technologies raises a serious challenge for traditional «mass» universities:

«Online — for mass universities this means a loss of monopoly on the storage and transfer of knowledge. And taking into account the fact that a lot of people come to the university for a certain set of competences, and not because they want to become part of the system, the question arises: why should these people continue to go to university? »

Some experts also noted that, as a possible consequence of the diversification of forms of education and the development of online opportunities, the trend of reducing the brand's importance to employers has gained momentum and this trend can become a threat to the most famous universities:

«Education in terms of which university you graduated from begins to play a really small role both for employers and for those projects that you have done, in comparison to what you have really learned. On the one hand, the university as a best owner of a set of received information decreases in its importance, as it has become more or less clear with the development of online education and with the opportunity to receive different knowledge in different locations. On the other hand, the university as a place where you immerse yourself in some community of people, where you are equally inundated amid in all social connections, this does not go away, but overall, I think we are already seeing the diminishing role of the university as a brand. This is happening in the technological world, probably during the course of the last two years. Resumes of those applicants for high-level positions without a classical education from a leading university, but who rather have a set of on-line and off-line courses (confirmed ones, that's important, they should have some certificates or something like that), are perceived quite receptively... Most likely, if it says that the certificate is from Harvard, it's even better, but difference between brand and non-brand is going away».

Several aspects of positive impact of online learning development are pointed out by the experts. First, in their opinion, the development of mass online education the emergence of quality MOOC (Mass Open Online Courses) provides public a chance to get quality education:

«What I'm witnessing is that there is an increasing development of education based on computers and what is available online. I suppose [this trend] will lead to a serious increase in competition [among universities] Bad education will leave the market. People will prefer to receive an average quality online education rather than a poor quality offline».

Moreover, the availability of MOOCs developed by the world's leading universities has had a significant impact on teaching technologies, and these solutions continue to improve, some experts point out.

«MOOC has a great future that has not been realized yet and it is connected with custom - tailored courses, as when, for instance, a computer can look at you, analyze your facial expression and on that basis offer something slower or faster, or suggest other exercises and tests»

However, among many experts the opinion prevails that MOOCs as such cannot give the student the same versatile training as good universities — first of all, because the personality of the graduate as a researcher or engineer, the bearer of «analytical, practical and creative intelligence» is formed to a decisive degree as the result of intensive interpersonal communication between the student and the professor both in the process of training, and in the process of carrying out research and applied projects. Thus the 'human' aspect is retained, the natural interaction between a mentor and a student maintained as a sort of 'sacred' trust.

«It's not enough just to teach people methods and facts. Students should learn to cover the entire problem mentally, and this cannot be learned without interacting with the person [the teacher]. I do not think that you can teach this — to teach to think — through the computer. It is also important to teach people to ask the right questions [that computers cannot do] ».

«The University still exists because it is sanctified by its formal title, and also because it gathers people into a dense space where they can get acquainted, get into the right environment. But this is all typical for leading universities, relatively speaking, Harvard in the US, the Higher School of Economics in Russia and so on. Therefore, leading universities won't ever have to compete with on-line technology. Because people do not go to Harvard for this».

To summarize, the most noticeable features of current Higher education system according to the respondents of this research are “growing importance of knowledge-led economies” which resulted in higher rate of population participation in Higher Education, increased global competition and online learning boom with its potential risks for the ‘mass’ universities and potential benefits in terms of quality education accessibility and teaching methods improvement.

3.2. Mission

Describing a university of the future, the experts envision its purpose as being an independent intellectual power body, which provides life-long learning options thus ensuring employability for the population in a long-term prospective.

3.2.1. Independent intellectual power

Independence from the state and involvement in the network is a promising trend to be regarded as essential. Many experts noted that such autonomy represents a vital criterion for the success of the university in the future. Therefore, the University of the Future must be able to be an independent center of intellectual power (although at the moment very many strong universities directly depend on the state and its funding, and therefore have no choice but to tolerate its intervention at the management level).

«The university is not merely an institution for training, it is not only a research institute, there should be a broader way of thinking, augmented by the capacity

to entertain and reflect on ideas from any scale, absolutely any scale — it is a very big ambition, and, unfortunately, this kind of thinking is intercepted by corporations, governments, many of whom deny that universities should have ideas, so it is already a struggle for intellectual power.»

In order to ensure a quick start and optimal positioning, it is crucial for any future university with similar missions to what is under discussion here to join, at an early stage, the necessary networks and partner programs with other, preferably well-established and even famous, universities. They must also form strategic alliances with employers that are household names to the public (UN, EU, large companies), as well as establishing cooperation and integration with international organizations such as UNICEF, Habitat, UNESCO.

Experts unanimously recommend avoiding the participation of government officials in the university governance. At the head of a successful university there should be a strong academician with excellent managerial qualities. According to experts, a hierarchical management system often becomes overloaded with levels and boards; a sufficient minimum set is as follows: supervisory board, president, provost (dean) and committees of professors (and students).

Speaking of the mission of universities, experts pay special attention to the importance of the role of leading independent intellectual centers capable of interpreting the global processes of any transformations occurring in society and formulating a «high-level» intellectual agenda for governments and social outcomes.

3.2.2. Life-long learning and employability

The dynamics of the processes taking place in the economy and in society leads to the necessity for a growing number of people to enter (and be adequately qualified for) several professions during the course of their lives. There is a growing need for a variety of forms of education for professionals who have a high level of basic training and considerable professional experience.

«People and students can choose relatively freely among modules and how they want to build their own curriculum and this works especially for guest students who would be accommodated for a year or a year and a half by foundations or organizations within the university when they are there and can pick up whatever they want provided that they have a project. This is the sort of ideal, universal education for the future and it works especially for people who already have 10-15 years of professional experience. It's much more difficult to accomplish in existing universities or in any existing curriculum because they are much more structured».

The experts believe, that university should provide access to advanced-quality higher education not only to a high-school graduate with no or very little professional experience, but also offer everyone concerned the opportunity to improve the skills and obtain the required knowledge of a specialist with many years of experience.

3.3. Vision of a *University of the Future*

Several essential features of “a university of the future” were listed by the respondents of this research. It is worth noting that some features e.g. internationalization, quality assurance that are being recognized by other research as exiting well established trends are reported by the experts as developing and desirable.

3.3.1. Ecosystem

The volume of applied research in the field of innovations carried out by the forces of distributed teams whose members interact through networks is growing in the world. The success of research universities — the elite among higher education — will in future depend on whether they can be important or central links in innovation ecosystems [7].

«The leading group of 300-400 universities in the world will be trying their best to build up and retain leadership competencies in research, with regard to their practical application; so they will attempt to occupy and represent the center of ecosystems (innovations). For example, KU Leuven, MIT, Stanford — these are universities that do not exist separately but are an important part of [such] ecosystems. I believe Cornell University in this sense is doomed. Cambridge built an ecosystem around itself, and Oxford most likely did not»

The «ecosystem» principle of organizing and conducting research and applied developments provides a chance to join the league of research universities successfully even for small institutions of higher education. For them it is important to occupy a certain niche in the ecosystem of innovations, to secure a leading place in any of the links. The rest of necessary knowledge and educational opportunities can be obtained from other elements of the system in the process of «symbiotic exchange» between the elements of the ecosystem.

«Nowadays, knowledge and competence can be at the intersection of field A and field B. It is possible and absolutely real, even if these fields A and B do not exist in one university — it can be in a distributed structure. This is a huge trend that I see»

Because of the dynamic nature of the processes in universities, which reflects the growing pace of changes in the economy and public life, an increasing number of professors and researchers start work on temporary contracts. This is in contrast to the almost lifelong guaranteed employment for university academics.

3.3.2. Balancing research and teaching and quality management

Experts point out the risk that the excessive focus of attention of the faculty on research may reduce their inclination to work with the students and therefore lead to a decrease in the quality of education [8].

«The public wants to know that their primary concern is opening doors, creating opportunities for their children. This is primary. Research is important but it's not a fundamental mission of what education should be about. Higher education is full of elite academics who have tenure, who don't care about their students and

who care about only publishing ideas in journals. They are all about the money and they're not doing a good job with our kids. There's a quote from a Senator in the US who says it very succinctly, he says: 'Higher education costs too much and delivers too little, it has to change'. That's the sentiment».

3.3.3. Internationalization

The globalization of economic life requires successful universities to be international in terms of the composition of university professors, students, and governing bodies. To succeed in competition for resources and international students (a source of income and prestige), a university must build an international community, attract strong professors and experts from all over the world, and be the focus of international intellectual life on the territory of their country.

«They (leading universities) understand that they need to be, not national, but global, in terms of both the student body and the body of professors serving them, and, further, in the system of management directing the process. This is because if you are not international, you cannot master certain types of knowledge — humanitarian and political, for example, and so you should have such a structure intrinsically. This is not an easy trend considering nationalism, Trump, etc. the Chinese are taking steps in this direction, but this remains a problematic trend, this is not just black and white»

3.3.4. Interdisciplinarity

Many experts draw attention to the fact that it is difficult for traditional universities with a conservative structure to overcome the inertia of the traditions of the last century, when the training was much more specialized and included a fairly rigid set of interrelated courses on specific topics.

«Most universities are a loose association of departments and chairs. Even the chairs within the department are very autonomous and interact with each other poorly. Interfaculty interaction basically comes down to administrative issues coordination, and not on teaching goals and strategies. In most universities, there is little real interdisciplinary education»

An example of a successful interdisciplinary program that is popular with students is the joint Bachelor of Science (hard sciences) and social sciences combination in Paris Sciences Po and UPMC.

«Students spend their 1st and 2nd years studying in Paris, and they take courses simultaneously at Sciences Po and UPMC. That is, they alternately enroll in the social sciences and humanities and in natural sciences. They literally, run between the two buildings. Sciences Po offers economics, modern history, political science and sociology, UPMC — biology, chemistry, computer science, mathematics and physics. During the second year of study, they choose minor — math — computer science, chemistry — biology or math — physics, while continuing to study the humanities and to work towards a social science major».

The experts noted the growing demand for higher education generalism — the formation among students of a broad and deep view of modern world problems, which will allow them to engage later on in private aspects of research and applied projects, thus preserving the vision of the overall perspective and global context of these projects

«The goal is to teach students to simultaneously understand and speak two languages — natural sciences (addressing various topics and issues) and social sciences. According to the organizers of the program, it is acquaintance with both that will allow students to adapt to the complex world of modern society. The program will give them skills that are useful for working in many industries: 1) they will learn the basic concepts of social sciences and the humanities; 2) they will be able to evaluate the arguments critically, being familiar their historical, economic, cultural and political context; 3) they will be able to combine arguments from two radically different paradigms — natural and social sciences; 4) build a system of argumentation, using knowledge from different disciplines.»

«I believe that in our time it is very important to reaffirm the traditional goal — that the university is the bearer of the European humanistic tradition, to recognize the importance of the breadth of education along with the specialization and focus on the global intellectual progress of society.»

«The concept of universality is even more important today than it was in the past, and the first two decades of the 21st century has witnessed a change in our understanding of the world we inhabit. We have come to see the fundamental pervasive importance of networks — of people, communities, devices, organisms, physical processes — where the elements of the network not only influence the dynamic of the network, but the network dynamics influence at a very deep level the behavior of the elements. This shift in understanding contrasts conventional control and hierarchical organization with self-organizing system dynamics. Specialization is still essential to understand and model the subject of interest, but system complexity matters more, especially when we go beyond pure science, engineering, and technology.»

3.3.5. Personalization and accessibility of education

Almost all experts believe that personalization of education is the leading trend in the development of higher education and in the future will become an important criterion for the success of any educational project. The expert opinion correlates well with Gallup research Group [9], where the main criterion for the success of higher education from the standpoint of graduates is the level of attention paid by professors to the students as individuals. On the one hand, online technologies have expanded the possibilities for universities, especially for small ones, allowing the creation of diverse educational programs. It is sufficient for the university to have specialists only in some subjects of the curriculum, and for other subjects to teach students online.

«They [ASU, Arizona State University, the largest university in the US, and NTU, Nanyang University of Technology in Singapore, a young university that is growing very fast in rankings] pay close attention to distance learning opportunities in online programs, the opportunity to deliver knowledge to a

person no matter where he is located. I think this is a very important trend. In this respect, a successful university of the future must be able to provide such an opportunity, for example — if we take the educational trajectory of a person that includes some knowledge of X, Y and Z, and only the field of knowledge X is taught at this university, it is necessary to help him to acquire knowledge in areas Y and Z».

3.3.6. Distributed campus

For launching international programs, the experts recommend using the distributed campus at the beginning of the project, where there is a physical building downtown with all the advantages of city life, and in addition a country pavilion, then possibly campuses in other cities of the world (thus a cross-border campus). Experts recommend not buying / constructing a campus but renting facilities. In a city where the main campus is located, there should be a high concentration of intellectual capital and a vibrant economy that provides job opportunities for graduates.

3.3.7. IT and Big Data

The spread of information technologies has led to a huge demand for training specialists, carrying out a large volume of applied research and implementing a growing number of applied projects on this topic.

«So without a doubt, the thing that will be most in demand for next 5 years is going to be data science and knowledge about how to develop new applications, creating value or innovations in all areas, not only in technical but also in the improvement of customer service to the citizens of the city. Banks are using it, so now big bankers massively downsize people, replacing them with computers instead. It is the biggest trend»

Working with «big data» has become an integral part of an increasing number of research and business areas. Knowledge and skills in this area are now virtually prerequisite for a specialist of any profile, they have gradually become an obligatory component of all educational programs.

«Big data for the foreseeable future is going to be very important in every field, given the massive amount of computer capacity that is now available. Humanities, social science, all areas of medicine, law, you name it, they all are using big data and of course marketing, banks — everybody out there is using big data, trying to figure out who their customers are, how best to get at them. Or looking back as a proactive exercise and, just to give a random example, doing analysis of some 19th century author and saying: «Oh, here is the phrase he used over and over again, this must have been important to him».

3.3.8. Humanities

Many experts agreed that in a world that is getting more and more complicated, university education should shape thinking in a broad sense, orient people towards the solution of the global issues that humanity faces. Extensive basic knowledge in different disciplines should be combined naturally with a deep expertise in concrete

subjects. A professional of the future should possess balanced knowledge and skills both in humanities and technical fields.

A number of experts believe that in the foreseeable future (albeit without an exact indication of when this may happen) the university system can expect a kind of «humanitarian renaissance» — an increase in demand for programs in social sciences and humanities. This is due to the need to study and manage complex systems that are socio-technical by their nature and a growing demand for soft skills and critical thinking, along with the increasing need of people to find their place in a world of robots and virtual reality.

«To continue teaching as actively as before in the fields where a human being can be replaced completely or for the most part by a computer, is senseless enough. We cannot fight with artificial intelligence and its computing power, it will be an ineffective investment of our energy, whereas it will, by contrast, be more effective to invest in areas where machines cannot replace us yet. That sphere is really more connected with liberal arts, with various soft skills and patterns of academic endeavor, and this is more connected with the humanitarian part».

«Without qualitative humanitarian knowledge, it will be impossible to live meaningfully in the future, because, on the one hand, these soft skills which employers are talking about are precisely those which graduates are lacking, and so future graduates must emerge from the universities having been brought up in the field of humanitarian education and joint project activities. On the other hand, there are growing problems of self-awareness in the domain of robots, in a world where professions that were well-known to human beings have radically changed over the past 10-15 years; therefore, people will need deeper social and psychological awareness, as well as various other insights into the grand scope of humanitarian knowledge.»

Hence a niche research university as an MVP-model, based on the experts' recommendations: With limited resources to launch the university, experts lean towards a model of a small university with a pronounced individual approach and a healthy, fruitful interdisciplinary environment for the work of researchers. The number of professors is small enough for sustainable life and development of the university (60-80 people), with no more than a 10 students per professor ratio. Education and research are concentrated around 4-5 majors, which work well at the junction with each other. For example, sociology / economics / IT, sociology / mathematics / IT. Practically all experts unanimously advise to include methods of working with big data both into the research agenda and in the academic program for all fields.

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Appendix 1. The list of respondents of in-depth interviews.

MATS NORDLUND has a background of executive positions in academia and industry in Europe, USA, and Russia. He spent 15 years in industry, first as director of corporate technology strategy and acquisition at Saab AB, a major aerospace company, and later as Director of Research and Development for Emerson Process Management — Level and Marine. In his academic career, Dr. Nordlund recently served three years as Vice President of Research Programs at Skoltech, a new university being established in Moscow in partnership with MIT. In the 1990s, he launched and managed the System Design and Management (SDM) program at MIT. Dr. Nordlund has also served on several national and international (EU) panels in innovation and research and as an industry member on Chalmers' Mechanical Engineering Program's Advisory board.

MAURIZIO SOBRERO is Full Professor of Innovation Management at the University of Bologna. He is a member of the Production and Operations Management Society. From 2000 to 2007 he was the Coordinator of the PhD program in Business Administration at the University. He has published 5 books and over 20 articles on the economy and international innovation management. He has taught in many programs for executives in South America, China and several European countries. In 2005 he was invited to contribute to the United Nations World Investment Report. He has done consulting for various companies and institutions. He is a member of the Board of Directors of the Zignago Vetro SpA where he oversees the Committee for Internal Control. He received his PhD in Management of Technology and Innovation at MIT (Massachusetts, USA).

DR. RUSSELL C. JONES has been a leader in several organizations; he has served as the Dean of Engineering at the University of Massachusetts, the Chairman of Civil Engineering at Ohio State University, Academic Vice President at Boston University, and President of the University of Delaware. He also published the International Engineering Education Digest for several years, with a distribution of 70,000 readers worldwide. In addition to his accomplishments within higher education, Dr. Jones has a long history within various engineering societies. He was the president of the American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE), president of the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology, as well as the Executive Director of the National Society of Professional Engineers. In 1998, Dr. Jones founded World Expertise LLC, a focused consulting company serving clients in higher education as they developed new programs and institutions.

DAVID VERNON is a Professor of cognitive robotics and computer vision at Carnegie Mellon University, Rwanda. Over the past 35+ years, he has held positions at Westinghouse Electric, Trinity College Dublin, European Commission, National University of Ireland, Maynooth, Science Foundation Ireland, Khalifa University, University of Genoa, Technical University of Munich, and University of Skovde. He is a Senior Member of the IEEE, a Chartered Engineer of the Institution of Engineers of Ireland, and a past Fellow of Trinity College Dublin. He is co-chair of the IEEE Robotics and Automation Technical Committee for Cognitive Robotics. BA, BAI Engineering, Trinity College Dublin PhD Computer Science, Trinity College Dublin

RICHARD K. MILLER has been President and first employee of Olin College of Engineering since 1999. Previously, he served as Dean of Engineering at the University of Iowa, Associate Dean of Engineering at USC in Los Angeles, and assistant professor of engineering at UCSB in Santa Barbara. With a background in applied mechanics and current interests in innovation in higher education, Miller is the author of more than 100 reviewed journal articles and other technical publications. He received the 2017 Brock International Prize in Education for his many contributions to the reinvention of engineering education in the 21st century. Together with two Olin colleagues, he received the 2013 Bernard M. Gordon Prize from the U. S. National Academy of Engineering (NAE) for Innovation in Engineering and Technology Education. Recently elected to the American Academy of Arts and Sciences, he is a member of both the NAE and the National Academy of Inventors. In 2011, he received the Marlowe Award for creative and distinguished administrative leadership from the American Society for Engineering Education. Miller currently serves as Chair of the National Academies Board on Higher Education and Workforce (BHEW). He has served as Chair of the Engineering Advisory

Committee of the U. S. National Science Foundation and has also served on advisory boards and committees for Harvard University, Stanford University, the NAE, NAS, and the U. S. Military Academy at West Point in addition to others. Furthermore, he has served as a consultant to the World Bank in the establishment of new universities in developing countries. A frequent speaker on engineering education, he received the 2002 Distinguished Engineering Alumnus Award from the University of California at Davis, where he earned his B. S. He earned his M. S. from MIT and Ph.D. from the California Institute of Technology, where he received the 2014 Caltech Distinguished Alumni Award.

JENS CHRISTIAN GODSKESSEN is a Provost at IT University of Copenhagen, the youngest University in Denmark.

ANDREAS FRIJDAL is an ex head of the European University Institute, having 29 years of service. He has been head of Academic Services for the last 25 of those years. Frijdal came to the EUI from Brussels in 1985 as a research officer. The Academic Service calculates that under his watch, more than 3000 researchers have passed through the Institute.

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